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Key Points:

- Diatom assemblages record multiannual to multidecadal changes in the timing, magnitude, and composition of phytoplankton blooms
- Fjord productivity is linked to climate variability and to associated changes in marine-terminating glaciers
- Higher fjord productivity coincided with warmer climate periods while the lowest productivity was recorded at the end of the Little Ice Age

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Climate Variability and Glacier Dynamics Linked to Fjord Productivity Changes Over the Last *ca.* 3300 Years in Nuup Kangerlua, Southwest Greenland

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Abstract Greenlandic fjords, located between the ice sheet and the ocean, are dynamic systems that can sustain highly variable levels of primary productivity and are sensitive to climate change. In our current climate trajectory, meltwater discharge is expected to significantly increase but its long-term effects on fjord productivity are still poorly constrained. Paleo-archives can offer valuable insights into long-term effects. Here, we present two marine sediment core records from Nuup Kangerlua, Southwest Greenland. Our goal is to better understand to what extent, and on what time-scales, climate fluctuations and associated glacier dynamic changes have impacted fjord productivity over the past *ca.* 3300 years. Our multiproxy records include diatom fluxes and assemblage composition, sediment biogeochemistry, and grain-size distribution. Our study reveals that fjord productivity is tightly linked to regional climate variability; relatively higher productivity levels coincided with mild climate periods whereas the climate cooling of the last millennium led to a decrease in productivity. The diatom records suggest that lower productivity is associated with shorter or less intense summer blooms, increased sea-ice cover and/or a stratified water column. Diatom assemblages demonstrate cold sea-surface conditions around 1600 CE that might be linked to local advance of glaciers. Cold conditions and decreasing productivity culminated at 1850 CE, when glaciers in the fjord retreated and high glacial meltwater discharge would have altered the fjord hydrography, likely leading to limited nutrient availability. Our long-term records support the idea that changing climate and cryosphere conditions have a non-linear impact on the productivity of Greenlandic fjords.

1. Introduction

Mass loss and meltwater runoff from the Greenland Ice Sheet (GrIS) have accelerated over the past four decades, particularly during the period 2000–2010 (Bevis et al., 2019; Mankoff, Noël, et al., 2020; Slater et al., 2021). A recent study estimated that 3.3% of the GrIS is committed to be lost, equivalent to ~0.3 m of global sea-level rise, regardless of the emission pathway humanity will follow (Box et al., 2022). The GrIS is estimated to currently discharge ~1,000 Gt⁻¹ of freshwater (Bamber et al., 2018) and ~480 Gt⁻¹ of solid ice per year (Mankoff, Noël, et al., 2020; Mankoff, Solgaard, et al., 2020) into the coastal areas around Greenland. Greenlandic fjords are gateways between the ice sheet and the ocean and, when able to sustain relatively high primary productivity, they can be key habitat for higher trophic levels and thus contribute to socioeconomic activities such as fisheries and local and indigenous livelihoods (Berthelsen, 2014; Cooley et al., 2022). Meltwater entering the fjords changes the water-column properties such as light and nutrients (mainly nitrate, phosphate, and silica), the availability of which affect primary productivity (Meire et al., 2016; Sejr et al., 2022).

Glacial meltwater runoff is typically poor in macronutrients, particularly nitrogen, which is the main nutrient limiting phytoplankton growth (Hopwood et al., 2020; Meire et al., 2017) in coastal Greenlandic waters. In fjord systems that receive sub-glacial discharge from marine-terminating glaciers, upwelling meltwater plumes entrain ambient nutrient-rich (nitrate-rich) deeper water to the surface, which can become available to primary producers (Hopwood et al., 2020; Meire et al., 2017). The magnitude and effects of upwelling meltwater plumes on phytoplankton theoretically depend on fjord topography and the grounding line depth of the marine-terminating glaciers (Hopwood et al., 2018). Recent fjord monitoring efforts have shown a positive impact of subglacial discharge on primary production reaching as far as 30–80 km down-fjord from the marine-terminating glaciers

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Figure 1. Nuup Kangerlua fjord system and location of studied sediment cores SA13-ST9-64G (64G) and SA13-ST6-36R (36R). Marine-terminating glaciers Kangiata Nunaata Sermia (KNS), Akullersuup Sermia (AS), Narsap Sermia (NS), and land-terminating glaciers Qamanaarsuup Sermia (QS), Kangilinnguata Sermia (KS), and Saqqap Sermia (SS) draining into the fjord. (a) Main fjord branch Nuup Kangerlua, (b) side branch Qoornup Sullua, (c) side branch Kapisillit Kangerluat, and (d) side branch Ummannap Sullua. Sill locations and outlines are from Mortensen et al. (2013).

(Meire et al., 2017), however, freshwater has also been found to influence marine productivity in glacier-distal fjord waters (Oksman et al., 2022). In contrast, fjords that receive meltwater only as surface runoff from land-terminating glaciers have typically a lower primary productivity, because of the lacking upwelling mechanism and because surface runoff increases stratification and water column turbidity (Hopwood et al., 2020; Meire et al., 2017; Sejr et al., 2022). While meltwater discharge into Greenlandic fjords is expected to increase in the future due to climate warming (Fettweis et al., 2013), its impacts on marine productivity—and subsequently on higher trophic levels—cannot be simply extrapolated (Hopwood et al., 2018).

Nuup Kangerlua (also known as Nuuk fjord or Godthåbsfjord) (64–65°N, 49–51°W) is the largest fjord system by surface area in Southwest Greenland (Figure 1). The 190-km long and 4–8 km wide Nuup Kangerlua consists of a main fjord and a network of side branches covering a total area of 2013 km². The fjord hosts three land-terminating glaciers (Qamanaarsuup Sermia; QS, Kangilinnguata Sermia; KS and Saqqap Sermia; SS) and three marine-terminating glaciers (Kangiata Nunaata Sermia, KNS; Akullersuup Sermia, AS; and Narsap Sermia, NS) (Figure 1). All three marine-terminating glaciers have experienced thinning and acceleration during the past two decades (Motyka et al., 2017). For KNS, which is the largest marine-terminating glacier in Southwest Greenland, the annual average discharge is ~5.2 Gt of solid ice and ~4.0 Gt of meltwater over the last 20 years (Mankoff, Noël, et al., 2020; Mankoff, Solgaard, et al., 2020), which travel out of the fjord mainly through the main fjord branch, Nuup Kangerlua (Figure 1). Nuup Kangerlua also receives surface runoff from several river outlets and lakes draining into the fjord, particularly Lake Tasersuaq that drains meltwater from SS (Figure 1).

Freshwater entering the fjord affects water temperature, salinity, and circulation patterns (Mortensen et al., 2011, 2013), and due to its large size, the fjord system exhibits a large inner fjord-offshore spatial gradient in surface ocean conditions (temperature and salinity) and in sea-ice conditions. In addition to large spatial variability, water temperature and salinity have significant seasonal and interannual variations, and observations between 2005 and 2018 have shown that temperatures varied between -1.04°C and 8.48°C and salinity between 18.48 and 34.37

PSU in the upper 300 m of the outer fjord (Mortensen et al., 2022). The innermost part of the fjord is covered by sea ice in winter (November–May) whereas the outer part, which is more influenced by the relatively warm and saline West Greenland Current, remains ice-free year round (Meire et al., 2017). Several sills exist in the fjord, particularly in the main fjord branch; two at the outer part of the fjord (at ~250 and 270 m depth) and a third one in the inner part ~21 km from the KNS terminus at ~170 m water depth (Figure 1; Mortensen et al., 2011).

Present-day annual primary production levels in Nuup Kangerlua are variable (~84.6–139.1 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) and the fjord has been regularly monitored for the past 15 years (e.g., Juul-Pedersen et al., 2015; Meire et al., 2017). There are typically two phytoplankton blooms occurring each year in Nuup Kangerlua (Juul-Pedersen et al., 2015) (a spring bloom and a late summer bloom). Nutrient availability following winter mixing and increased solar radiation initiate the spring bloom, which is followed by a second bloom in late summer triggered by subglacial freshwater discharge. A recent study has shown that the summer bloom is not solely maintained by subglacial meltwater but that fjord circulation also plays an important role (Stuart-Lee et al., 2023). Diatoms are the most abundant group of marine phytoplankton and the main primary producers in the Arctic region (Poulin et al., 2011). Along the West Greenland coast, diatoms have been shown to display a strong link with marine food-web dynamics (Krawczyk et al., 2021). Diatoms exhibit a species-specific sensitivity to sea-surface parameters (sea ice, temperature, and salinity) and in Nuup Kangerlua, diatom assemblages have a strong seasonal succession with changes in species composition mainly driven by physical parameters (salinity, temperature, and light) rather than nutrients (Krawczyk, Witkowski, et al., 2015; Luostarinen et al., 2020). A recent 1-year sediment trap deployment at 300 m water-depth in the fjord recorded peak biogenic silica and diatom export fluxes from May to August (Luostarinen et al., 2020).

The impact of glacial meltwater on fjord productivity has been the subject of several recent studies that have contributed to process-level understanding and decadal-scale insights (e.g., Holding et al., 2019; Hopwood et al., 2020; Meire et al., 2016, 2017; Sejr et al., 2022). However, only longer-term records that reach beyond the modern warming (Oksman et al., 2022) can help placing productivity trends into a wider temporal context and, more generally, evaluating the long-term effects of cryosphere changes on high latitude ecosystems. Fjord productivity in Nuup Kangerlua is affected by freshwater discharge entering the fjord, and recent work covering the past century has shown that modern high productivity levels have prevailed only since the late 1990s (Oksman et al., 2022). Here, we aim to extend Nuup Kangerlua fjord productivity records back to the past three millennia. We assess how climate fluctuations between relatively warmer and cooler periods, and associated changes in local glacier dynamics, have influenced fjord productivity over time by using a multiproxy approach including bulk sediment biogeochemistry, grain-size distribution and diatom species composition and fluxes. We discuss our proxy records in the light of regional climate reconstructions and geological evidence for historical glacier ice-margin fluctuations in the Nuup Kangerlua area.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sediment Core Records

Sediment cores SA13-ST9-64G and SA13-ST6-36R (hereafter referred to as 64G and 36R) were collected in two of the Nuup Kangerlua side branches on board the Greenlandic research vessel *Sanna* in 2013 (Seidenkrantz et al., 2014). We selected side branches of the fjord because these are areas of accumulation of sediments with low disturbance, as opposed to the main fjord branch, which is the main route for iceberg export toward the shelf. The 497 cm-long gravity core 64G was recovered from 413 m water depth in the Qoornup Sullua branch (64° 19.4360'N; 51° 16.4756'W), while the 96-cm long Rumorh-lot core 36R was retrieved at 398 m water depth from the Kapisillit Kangerluat branch (64° 29.076'N; 50° 42.553'W) (Figure 1). Both sediment cores were stored in the cold (2–3°C) before opening and sampling, and all subsamples were frozen and freeze-dried before analyses.

2.2. Geochronology

The chronology of 64G is based on 10 AMS ¹⁴C dates (Table 1) from benthic foraminifera and organic material (polychaete worm tubes). The chronology of core 36R is compiled using previously published ²¹⁰Pb and ¹³⁷Cs measurements (Oksman et al., 2022) and three additional ¹⁴C dates on organic material (Table 1). Sediment core 36R is also referred to by its site number, as “site 6” in Oksman et al. (2022). Age-depth models were created using the OxCal 4.4 program (Bronk Ramsey, 2009; Bronk Ramsey & Lee, 2013) and by calibrating ages using the Marine20 calibration curve (Heaton et al., 2020) and a ΔR of -70 ± 54 (Pieńkowski et al., 2022). In this

Table 1
Radiocarbon Dates and Calibrations From Cores 64G and 36R

Core	Sample ID	Depth (cm)	Material	¹⁴ C age (year BP)	+/-	Calibrated age range (2-sigma)	Modeled median age (cal. year BP)
64G	AAR_31349	6	Organic material (worm tube)	583	32	-63-267	75
64G	ETH 126099.1.1	32-33	Mixed benthic foraminifera	750	70	53-482	241
64G	ETH 126100.1.1	68-69	Mixed benthic foraminifera	950	110	188-690	444
64G	AAR_31350	72	Organic material (worm tube)	1,359	61	633-1,026	Outlier
64G	ETH 110880.1.1	124-125	Mixed benthic foraminifera	1,310	40	610-945	737
64G	ETH 110881.1.1	176-177	Mixed benthic foraminifera	1,485	50	738-1,148	981
64G	ETH 110882.1.1	256-257	Mixed benthic foraminifera	1,875	60	1,134-1,554	1,409
64G	ETH 127461.1.1	308-309	Mixed benthic foraminifera	1,855	300	700-2065	1,777
64G	AAR_31351	455	Organic material (worm tube)	3,218	33	2749-3,155	2966
64G	ETH 106032.1.1	496-497	Mixed benthic foraminifera	3,595	60	3,170-3,654	3,334
36R	AAR_30041	18.5	Organic material (worm tube)	479	26	-63-39	66
36R	AAR_30042	50	Organic material (worm tube)	809	28	150-495	364
36R	AAR_31353	94	Organic material (worm tube)	1,317	33	620-945	780

context we note that while Heaton et al. (2020) advised caution when using Marine20 in polar regions, the same issue is true for Marine13 (Reimer et al., 2013), and subsequently, Heaton et al. (2022) strongly recommended using Marine20, and state that there are likely minimal issues for the Holocene period in (sub)polar regions.

2.3. Grain-Size Analysis

The distribution of the particle fractions were analyzed with two complementary methods. The clay and silt (<63 μm), fine sand (63–150 μm), and coarse sand (>150 μm) were analyzed using wet-sieving method on a total of 137 samples (82 samples from 64G and 55 samples from 36R) using a minimum of 2 g of freeze-dried sediment. More detailed information on the distribution of clay (<2 μm) and silt (2–63 μm) was obtained on 62 samples from 64G and 55 samples from 36R by conducting laser diffraction analyses on a Malvern Mastersizer E/2000. All samples used for laser diffraction analyses consisted of 0.2 g of freeze-dried sediment and were treated with a sodium pyrophosphate decahydrate-solution and ultrasonicated once for 2 min to separate aggregates before measurements were conducted.

2.4. Biogeochemical Analysis

The total organic carbon (TOC), total nitrogen, and the isotopic composition of bulk organic carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and nitrogen ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) were measured from core 64G on 65 samples at the IRMS lab at the Department of Geosciences and Natural Resources Management, University of Copenhagen, Denmark. Approximately 20 mg of bulk sediment per sample were homogenized before measuring by Dumas combustion (1,700°C) on an elemental analyzer (CE 1110, Thermo Electron, Milan, Italy or Flash 2000, Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany). The EA was coupled in continuous flow mode to a Finnigan MAT Delta PLUS or Thermo Delta V Advantage isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany). From 36R, TOC was measured on 46 samples using a LECO CS-200 instrument at the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland. Samples consisted of 300 mg of freeze-dried sediment and were treated with 5 ml of 37% hydrochloric acid (HCl) in an incubator for 1 hr at 65°C and centrifuged three times and rinsed with demineralized water before measurement to remove inorganic carbon.

Biogenic silica (BSi) contents were measured at the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland using the weak base (Na_2CO_3) extraction method (DeMaster, 1991) on 74 and 51 samples from 64G and 36R, respectively. About 30 mg of freeze-dried sediment were leached in an 85°C water bath using 40 ml 1% sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3). Subsamples of 1 ml were taken after 3, 4, and 5 hr of extraction and measured with a spectrophotometer Jenway 7305 using the blue ammonium-molybdate method (Mullin & Riley, 1955). Biogenic silica concentrations were calculated with the basic assumption that mineral-derived silica dissolves at a constant rate

Figure 2. Sedimentation rates and age-depth models for sediment cores 64G (a) and 36R (b). Gray shaded areas represents the 95% probability range of the modeled ages calculated using Oxcal, which follows a Bayesian stratigraphy-constrained approach.

throughout the extraction whereas the biogenic silica dissolves within the first 2 hr (Barão et al., 2015). Biogenic silica fluxes were obtained by accounting for variations in sedimentation rates through time.

2.5. Diatoms

A total of 131 and 47 diatom microscope slides were prepared from 64G and 36R, respectively, following the method by Battarbee et al. (2001). All samples were treated with 10% hydrochloric acid (HCl) and 30% hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) in an 80°C water bath for 4 hr to remove carbonates and organic material. Afterward, 0.1 ml of a microsphere solution of 6.13×10^6 microspheres ml^{-1} was added to the samples. Microscope slides were mounted using Naphrax® with a refractive index of 1.73 and analyzed with an Olympus BX51 light microscope using phase contrast optics at 1,000× magnification. A minimum of 300 diatom valves were counted (excluding *Chaetoceros*). Specimens of the genus *Chaetoceros* were left out of the assemblage percentage counts as these taxa are common in marine environments and the genus is well-adapted to a wide spectrum of environmental conditions (Koç-Karpuz & Schrader, 1990). Diatom concentrations (valves g^{-1} dry sediment) were calculated using the sum of microspheres counted per total diatom sum and the number of microspheres added in the diatom sample. The non-linear ordination method of correspondence analysis (CA) was utilized using the program PAST version 4.02 (Hammer et al., 2001) to detect ecological shifts and the major patterns of variation in the diatom assemblages. This method is generally considered suitable for representing community responses to highly dynamic environments (e.g., Legendre & Legendre, 1998). The CA was run on relative abundance data for all taxa representing >1%, and the resulting sample scores for axis 1 give a measure of the ecological response of the community to environmental changes over time.

3. Results

3.1. Geochronology and Grain-Size Distribution

The 497-cm-long sediment core 64G covers the past ca. 3.3 cal ka BP (hereafter ka BP) with sedimentation rates varying between 0.1 and 0.2 cm yr^{-1} (Figure 2). Sedimentation rates are stable in the bottom part of the core and increase at 308 cm depth (dated to ca. 1.7 ka BP) with the highest sedimentation rates occurring between 116 and 176 cm depth (ca. 0.9–0.7 ka BP) and then decreasing toward the top of the core. The 96 cm long sediment core 36R covers the past ca. 0.78 ka BP (from ca. 1160 CE) with sedimentation rates varying from 0.1 to 0.27 cm yr^{-1} (Figure 2). Sedimentation rates are stable from the bottom of the core until 20 cm core-depth (dated to ca. 1870 CE) and then increase toward the top of the core.

Both sediment cores consist mainly of fine-grained sediments (<63 μm) which vary from 81.4% to 99.4% in 64G and from 61.8% to 96.8% in 36R (Figure 3). In 64 G, the majority of the fine fraction consists of silt (2–63 μm ; varying between 75.7% and 80.1%) and clay (<2 μm ; varying between 1.9% and 21.8%). In 36 R, the proportion of silt (2–63 μm) varies from 28.8% to 69.3% and clay (<2 μm) from 13.0% to 70.1% (Figure 3). The coarse grain sediment fraction (>63 μm) ranges from 0.2% to 18.6% in 64G and from 3.2% to 38.3% in 36R (Figure 3).

3.2. Biogeochemical Analysis

Total organic carbon (TOC) ranges from 1.6 to 2.6 wt% in 64G (Figure 3) and from 0.5 to 0.9 wt% in 36R, whereas TOC fluxes in 64G and 36R vary from 2.3 to 4.0 $\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ and from 0.6 to 2.2 $\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$, respectively (Figure 3). Total nitrogen (TN) content and nitrogen and carbon isotopes ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$) were measured only for core 64G. TN in 64G vary between 0.23% and 0.34%, yielding C/N-ratios from 6.4 to 8.2 (Figure 3) which are typical values for marine phytoplankton (Meyers, 1994). Nitrogen isotope ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) values vary between 3.5 and 5.6‰ and carbon isotope ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) values range from -21.5 to -23.2 ‰ (Figure 3), resulting in values that are close to those typical of aquatic organic matter (-22 and -20 ‰) (Meyers, 1994), suggesting that they are only slightly enriched toward terrestrial organic matter. The measured biogenic silica (BSi) content of the sediments varies between 24.4 and 48.7 mg g^{-1} (mean 32.1 mg g^{-1}) in 64G and between 12.8 and 34.5 mg g^{-1} (mean 23.3 mg g^{-1}) in 36R (Figure 3), whereas BSi fluxes in 64G and 36R vary from 3.7 to 6.4 $\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ and from 1.7 to 7.2 $\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$, respectively (Figure 3).

3.3. Diatoms

Diatoms are generally very abundant in both records; estimated total diatom concentrations vary from 1.9 to 27.6×10^6 valves g^{-1} in 64G and from 2.3 to 35.8×10^6 valves g^{-1} in 36R, and fluxes from 0.2 to 4.3×10^6 valves $\text{g}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$ and from 0.2 to 3.7×10^6 valves $\text{g}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$, respectively (Figure 4). The diatom assemblages in both cores are dominated by *Fragilariopsis oceanica*, *Thalassiosira antarctica* var. *borealis* (including both resting spores and vegetative cells), the resting spore of *Detonula confervacea*, *Thalassiosira nordenskiöldii*, *Fragilariopsis cylindrus*, *Rhizosolenia hebetata* f. *semispina*, *Synedra* spp., *Cocconeis costata*, and *Cocconeis scutellum* (Figure 4). Diatom species were grouped based on their known ecological preferences into five groups: summer-bloom species, early-spring bloom species, sea-ice associated species, benthic species, and freshwater species. The summer-bloom species group consists mainly of large centric diatoms that prefer relatively cold waters and typically bloom in the late summer (Krawczyk, Arendt, et al., 2015; Luostarinen et al., 2020; Oksman et al., 2019). Early-spring bloom species consist of pennate species that prefer cold and fresher waters that occur in the spring during and right after the sea-ice breaks up and melts (von Quillfeldt, 2000, 2004; Weckström et al., 2020). Sea-ice associated species are numerous in high sea-ice concentrations or are known to produce sea-ice related biomarkers (Belt et al., 2017; Oksman et al., 2019; Weckström et al., 2020). Benthic species live in the coastal region on the sea floor or attached to substrates (Cremer, 1998; Foged, 1973; Pearce et al., 2014). Freshwater species live in freshwater environment and do not inhabit the marine environment (Cremer, 1998; Foged, 1973). *Chaetoceros* spp. are highly abundant in both cores and dominate the diatom assemblages with concentrations from 0.3 to 7.2×10^6 valves g^{-1} in 64G and from 0.5 to 8.5×10^6 valves g^{-1} in 36R (Figure 4). *Chaetoceros* flux rates vary from 0.1 to 0.9×10^6 valves $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ in 64G and from 0.1 to 1.2×10^6 valves $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ in 36R (Figure 4).

Diatom CA sample score values for axis 1 display significant shifts in the diatom assemblage and reflect changes in the environmental conditions controlling the diatom assemblage. The CA sample scores for axis 1 for 64G remain relatively stable and slightly positive from 3.3 ka BP until ca. 0.5 ka BP (1450 CE), when scores shift toward negative values, accentuated after ca. 0.19 ka BP (1750 CE) (Figure 4). The CA sample scores for axis 1 for the 36R diatom assemblage show a gradual change over the studied time period, with a switch from negative to positive score values at ca. 1750 CE (Figure 4).

4. Discussion

4.1. Mild Climate and Glacial Melt Sustained Fjord Productivity During the Early Neoglacial

Sediment core 64G, covering the past ca. 3300 years, displays decadal and centennial scale fluctuations in both sea-surface conditions and fjord productivity in Nuup Kangerlua (Figure 5). Sediment BSi and TOC concentrations indicate a gradual decrease in fjord productivity from relatively high sedimentary concentrations during

Figure 3. Grain size distribution (Malvern and wet-sieving methods, respectively), biogenic silica (BSi) content and fluxes, total organic carbon (TOC) content in 64G (a) and 36R (b), and total nitrogen, C/N-ratio and isotopic composition of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ in 64G. For the wet-sieving data from 64G, broken axis is used to make changes in larger grain sizes visible.

Figure 4. CA sample scores for axis 1 (dashed line marks the “0”), diatom concentrations and fluxes, relative abundance (%) of diatom groups: (spring-bloom species, summer-bloom species, benthic species, sea-ice associated species, and freshwater species), relative abundance (%) of the most common species in each core, *Chaetoceros* and chrysophyte cyst concentrations and fluxes in cores 64G (a) and 36R (b). Dashed lines mark the timing of the Medieval Climate Anomaly (MCA) and the Little Ice Age (LIA) climate periods.

the early Neoglacial period (between 3.3 and 2 ka BP) toward the lowest productivity levels at the end of the Little Ice Age (LIA) at ca. 0.1 ka BP (Figure 5). The gradually decreasing trend in diatom productivity follows the late-Holocene northern hemisphere cooling (Kaufman et al., 2020) shown by regional climate records (temperature and precipitation) (Allan et al., 2021; D’Andrea et al., 2011; Thomas et al., 2016) that has been suggested to be mainly driven by decreasing hemispheric insolation (Berger & Loutre, 1991). In contrast to the gradually decreasing trend in BSi and TOC concentrations, the BSi and TOC fluxes, which account for changes in the sedimentation rates (Figure 2), suggest that the long-term Neoglacial productivity trend was relatively stable or even increased during the past millennium (Figure 5). These contradictory trends between concentrations and fluxes are controlled by the sedimentation rates, which are better constrained for the upper part of the core (from ca. 1.7 ka BP to core top) and assume steady sedimentation rates for the period between 3.3 and 1.7 ka BP (Figure 2). Diatom valve concentrations and fluxes are relatively stable and do not show major fluctuations until ca. 0.1 ka BP (Figure 5), which suggests relatively stable diatom productivity between 3.3 and 0.1 ka BP.

Despite the trends in recorded biogeochemical proxies and diatoms not being fully consistent (likely due to site- and proxy-specific differences in vertical export dynamics and preservation), all productivity proxies (BSi, TOC,

Figure 5.

and diatom concentrations and fluxes) indicate increased values between 2.8 and 3.3 and from 2.0 to 2.4 ka BP (Figure 5). Diatom assemblages in core 64G indicate relatively mild and saline sea-surface conditions in Nuup Kangerlua between 3.3 and 2 ka BP, which supports the BSi and TOC concentrations that suggest relatively high fjord productivity at the time, accompanied by peaks in *Chaetoceros* and other diatom taxa (Figure 5). The diatom assemblage is mainly dominated by *T. antarctica* var. *borealis* vegetative cells (Figure 4), which is a typical late-summer bloomer that also tolerates relatively high salinities (Jiang et al., 2001). Evidence of relatively mild sea-surface temperatures is provided by peaks of *Thalassionema nitzschioides* in the diatom record at this time (Figure 5). This species follows the warm, saline North Atlantic Current flow in the North Atlantic (Jiang et al., 2001; Krawczyk et al., 2010, 2014; Oksman et al., 2019) and is an indicator of warmer, and possibly Atlantic-sourced waters, at Arctic latitudes. The relatively mild climate conditions suggested by the high abundance of summer blooming centric species (Figure 4) are in line with other paleorecords from southwest Greenland suggesting mild early Neoglacial climate conditions in the Kangerlussuaq region (D'Andrea et al., 2011), increased precipitation (Thomas et al., 2016) at the West Greenland coast, and higher sea-surface temperatures at the Southwest Greenland shelf (Allan et al., 2021). Ocean heat fluxes are important drivers of glacial melt (Bendtsen et al., 2015) and the mild oceanic and atmospheric conditions likely promoted glacial melt at the time leading to enhanced productivity. In fjords with marine-terminating glaciers, summer productivity has been linked to subglacial meltwater discharge that provides critical upwelling of nutrient-rich deep-water (e.g., Kanna et al., 2022; Meire et al., 2017). Presently, summer blooms in Nuup Kangerlua account for a significant fraction (35%–40%) of the annual production, that was estimated to be up to $120 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ in 2013 (Juul-Pedersen et al., 2015; Meire et al., 2015). Summer-time subglacial discharge, which is essential for the summer bloom, typically coincides with the annual maximum meltwater runoff, possibly enhanced by wind-driven upwelling (Meire et al., 2017). Freshwater input has been shown to affect the long-term bloom dynamics in the fjord (Oksman et al., 2022) and the high percentage of the late-summer bloomers (Figure 4) suggests increased summer melting during the early Neoglacial.

Geological evidence from southwest Greenland suggests that the GrIS was smaller than today during the Mid-Holocene, when air temperatures in Greenland were 1–3°C warmer than twentieth century averages (Briner et al., 2016; Young & Briner, 2015). Modeling efforts place the ice margin significantly behind its modern-day extent at this time, possibly >30 km inland (Lecavalier et al., 2014), however, these might be overestimated as models do not consider dynamic processes that control the marine-terminating parts in deep troughs (such as Nuup Kangerlua), and geological records have instead suggested that ice margins remained relatively stable and close to their current extent (Levy et al., 2017; Young & Briner, 2015). For KNS, a large >30 km retreat inland from its modern-day position would mean the ice margin was land-terminating (Figure 7) which would likely have had an effect on fjord productivity (Hopwood et al., 2020; Meire et al., 2017). However, we find no evidence in our record supporting that the presently marine-terminating glaciers (KNS, AS or NS) would have retreated onto land during the early Neoglacial. Our record rather suggests a relatively warm and productive fjord environment with (subglacial) meltwater entering the fjord. In addition, warm conditions and meltwater discharge are supported by the increased numbers of *Chrysophyte* cysts (Figure 4) that have been linked to warmer temperatures and to a fjord summer bloom with renewal of nutrients due to meltwater release at depth (Krawczyk, Arendt, et al., 2015; Krawczyk, Witkowski, et al., 2015) possibly also enhanced by wind-driven upwelling. The presence of freshwater diatom species in a marine record (Figure 4) can also be indicative of freshwater runoff as these species do not inhabit the marine environment but can get flushed into the fjord via terrestrial runoff. Additionally, the high percentage of fine particles in the sediment (Figure 3) and high number of benthic diatoms (Figure 4) could mean an increase in water turbidity. Meltwater discharge has been suggested to have a negative impact on primary production as glacial turbid sediment plumes contain high concentrations of fine glacial flour that reduces light availability (Meire et al., 2017; Murray et al., 2015). However, these conditions can favor benthic diatom species as they can tolerate high water turbidity, hold the ability to adjust to different light conditions, and exploit

Figure 5. (a) BSi concentrations and fluxes in core 64G, (b) TOC concentrations and fluxes in core 64G, (c) diatom concentrations and fluxes in core 64G, (d) *Chaetoceros* concentrations and fluxes in core 64G, (e) Greenland Ice Sheet summit temperature record based on argon and nitrogen isotopes in the GISP2 ice core (Kobashi et al., 2017) and summer insolation for 65°N (Berger & Loutre, 1991), (f) alkenone-based (Uk37) temperature reconstruction from Kangerlussuaq (D'Andrea et al., 2011), (g) precipitation record ($\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{aq}}$) from West Greenland (Thomas et al., 2016), (h) relative abundance of benthic diatom species in 64G, (i) relative abundance of *Thalassionema nitzschioides* in core 64G, and (j) relative abundance of *Rhizosolenia hebetata* f. *semispina* in core 64G. Approximate timings of Neoglacial, Roman Warm Period (RWP), Dark Ages Cold Period (DACP), Medieval Climate Anomaly (MCA), and the Little Ice Age (LIA) climate events identified from Greenland Ice Sheet ice cores (Dahl-Jensen et al., 1998) are indicated in the bottom of the figure.

Figure 6.

nutrients from deeper waters (down to ca. 200–300 m) (Glud et al., 2002) which highlights their importance for primary productivity under conditions that otherwise could limit it.

4.2. Climate Fluctuations Impact Fjord Productivity

As climate cooled during the Neoglacial, southwest Greenland glaciers and ice margins were advancing (Larsen et al., 2017; Lasher et al., 2020; Levy et al., 2017), yet the precise timing and extent of the advances are not well constrained. During the period between 2.8 and 2.4 ka BP, a drop in TOC and BSi sedimentary contents (Figure 5) together with lower nitrogen isotope ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) values (Figure 3) suggest reduced phytoplankton productivity, while the relative abundance of sea-ice associated diatom species becomes slightly higher (Figure 4), indicating a more extensive sea-ice season. It is possible that more pronounced sea-ice conditions also assisted temporary glacier growth by supporting the glacier frontlines. Similarly, formation of seasonal sea ice after ca. 2.7 ka BP has been documented from a sediment core record from the neighboring Ameralik fjord (Seidenkrantz et al., 2007). Generally, increases in sea-ice cover have been shown to decrease pelagic net primary productivity in shallow coastal areas (Møller et al., 2023). The cold climate conditions in the region may have restricted summertime melting leading to nutrient depletion in the surface waters as indicated by the relatively low abundances of *Chaetoceros* (Figure 5). *Chaetoceros* species typically bloom late in the summer and represent the last productive stage in Arctic fjords (von Quillfeldt, 2000; Krawczyk et al., 2014, 2015b), and correspond to high concentrations of dissolved nutrients and thus also reflect surface water productivity (Cremer, 1999).

Our proxies show a decline in fjord productivity at ca. 2.1 ka BP (Figure 5), coinciding with cooling air and sea-surface temperatures in West Greenland (D'Andrea et al., 2011; Moros et al., 2006). All productivity proxies, TOC, BSi, and diatom concentrations and fluxes, declined ca. 2.1 ka BP suggesting lower productivity (Figure 5). Changes in the diatom assemblage composition (Figure 4) also indicate a transition to cooler climate. The abundance of late-summer bloomers, which prefer warm and nutrient-rich waters, for example, *T. antarctica* var *borealis* (vegetative cell) and *Chrysophyte* cysts, declined, whereas the relative abundance of species associated with cooler and slightly fresher conditions, for example, *Thalassiosira anguste-lineata*, *Thalassiosira hyalina* and *T. nordenskiöldii* (Jensen et al., 2004; Oksman et al., 2019), increased (Figure 4). The assemblage shift indicates increased stratification that could be linked to less vigorous meltwater-driven circulation in the fjord or a change in wind patterns. This change in the sea-surface conditions and productivity is consistent with a wider regime shift in regional climate that has also been detected in northern Baffin Bay, and linked to the Arctic Oscillation (Limoges et al., 2020; Ribeiro et al., 2021).

Several episodes of land-terminating glacier and ice cap advances are known to have occurred between 1.6 and 1.2 ka BP across southwest Greenland; these have been linked to regional cooling trends (Larocca et al., 2020; Larsen et al., 2017; Levy et al., 2017; Schweinberg et al., 2018). Productivity proxies (BSi and TOC) and diatom assemblages record only minor changes in Nuup Kangerlua during this time interval. Otherwise, our record does not provide evidence of large marine-terminating glacier advances similar to the LIA advance which is more clearly demonstrated in the diatom assemblages and sedimentary proxies (Figure 5), and thus, it is likely that Nuup Kangerlua's glaciers remained relatively stable around their modern-day position until advancing at the onset of the LIA.

During the most pronounced warm period of the Late Holocene, the Medieval Climate Anomaly (MCA) between 1.0 and 0.7 ka BP (~950–1250 CE), air temperatures in Greenland were slightly higher than pre-industrial levels (Kaufman et al., 2020) and glaciers and ice caps close to Nuup Kangerlua retreated to their Holocene minimum extent (Larsen et al., 2017). Our record shows increase in BSi and TOC fluxes and in diatom and *Chaetoceros* fluxes (Figure 5) that are consistent with increased fjord productivity over the MCA. The productive fjord environment might have assisted the human occupation of the area by providing marine resources as it coincides

Figure 6. (a) KNS terminus extent in relation to its modern (2020) position (Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, van, et al., 2014; Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, van, et al., 2014; Weidick et al., 2012). Dashed line with question marks indicates the period where KNS terminus position is not well constrained. (b) Greenland Ice Sheet summit temperature record based on argon and nitrogen isotopes in GISP2 ice core (Kobashi et al., 2017), (c) southern Greenland summer precipitation record ΔRH (%) from Lake 578 (Zhao et al., 2022), (d) BSi content and fluxes in 36R, (e) TOC in 36R, (f) diatom fluxes in 36R, (g) diatom correspondence analysis (CA) axis 1 scores in 36R (dashed line indicates “0”), (h) IRD (>63 μm) in 36R, (i) BSi content and fluxes in 64G, (j) TOC in 64G, (k) diatom fluxes in 64G, (l) diatom CA axis 1 scores in 64G (dashed line indicates “0”), and (m) IRD (>63 μm) in 64G. Blue shaded area marks period of cold and harsh climate conditions between 1600 and 1900 CE. Solid line marks the latest time KNS reached its LIA maximum extent and dashed box marks the timing of the LIA retreat phase (ca. 1800–1900 CE).

Figure 7. (a) Map of KNS frontline changes and modeled stability from Pearce et al. (2022). (b) KNS frontline position in relation to fjord bathymetry. Bathymetrical data was retrieved from BedMachine v5 (Morlighem et al., 2021). Blue (red) marks margin positions during advance (retreat) phases.

with the establishment of the Norse Western Settlement (D'Andrea et al., 2011; Dugmore et al., 2012). The relative abundance of thermophilic species, *Thalassionema nitzschioides*, remained relatively high over the MCA (Figure 5) suggesting relatively warm sea-surface temperatures at site 64G. Similarly, high abundances of warm-water species were observed in a diatom record from Holsteinsborg Dyd (off SW Greenland), which was suggested to be caused by either increased inflow of Atlantic waters or sea-surface warming (Sha et al., 2011). However, the most notable increase is in the abundance of *R. hebetata* f. *semispina* (Figure 4) suggesting converging water masses and a stratified water column. *Rhizosolenia* species are related to productive marine

environments and are abundant along oceanic frontal zones where warm and cold waters meet (similar conditions to glacial meltwater pulses) (Andersen et al., 2004; Kemp et al., 2006; Krawczyk, Arendt, et al., 2015; Oksman et al., 2019). Also, the *Chaetoceros* taxon, which is linked to productive surface waters, for example, in upwelling areas (Cremer, 1999; Crosta et al., 1997; Koç-Karpuz & Jansen, 1992) has relatively higher abundances at this point. Transport of moisture and warm air into southwest Greenland increased summer precipitation after 1.1 ka BP (Figure 5; Zhao et al., 2022) that likely enhanced glacier melt, as seen as the highest sedimentation rates of the record (Figure 3), and would have created favorable conditions for the *Rhizosolenia* blooms and relatively productive summer season.

4.3. Reduced Fjord Productivity Linked to Late-Neoglacial Climate Cooling and Glacier Advance

Not taking the MCA or modern warming into account, atmospheric conditions in Greenland gradually became dryer and cooler over the past millennium (Lasher & Axford, 2019; Zhao et al., 2022), and marine records from south and west Greenland indicate cooling sea-surface temperatures and increased sea-ice concentrations (Roncaglia & Kuijpers, 2004; Seidenkrantz et al., 2007; Sha et al., 2011, 2016). Moreover, multiple studies report glacier margin advances in Nuup Kangerlua during the LIA (Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, As, et al., 2014; Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, Weidick, et al., 2014; Levy et al., 2017; Pearce et al., 2022; Weidick et al., 2012). All productivity proxies (TOC, BSi, and diatoms) in our two sediment records show large fluctuations during the past millennium (Figure 6). Fjord productivity in Nuup Kangerlua gradually decreased along with climate cooling, culminating at the end of the LIA at ca. 1850 CE, yet this decreasing trend was rapidly reversed after 1900 CE (Figure 6).

The KNS frontline position is one of the best constrained in terms of historical glacier frontline changes in Greenland (Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, As, et al., 2014; Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, Weidick, et al., 2014; Pearce et al., 2018, 2022; Weidick et al., 2012; Young et al., 2021). The neighboring AS (Figures 1 and 7) is known to be confluent with KNS for most of the past millennium, whereas NS has been stable after the LIA and remained close to its maximum extent until 2009 (Figure 7; Motyka et al., 2017). Any possible fluctuations in the NS frontline position before the LIA are unknown. Of the Nuup Kangerlua glaciers, KNS has substantially the largest solid and freshwater discharge (Motyka et al., 2017) and can thus be considered as having the most significant impact on the fjord hydrography and productivity.

The KNS front has been shown to advance already between 994 and 1165 CE (ca. 0.9 ka BP), when it blocked the draining route of lake Isvand toward the northwest leaving the lake to drain toward Austmannadalen (Figure 7) (Pearce et al., 2022). The timing of this advance is consistent with cooling of the ocean surface temperatures ca. 1000 CE as indicated by our diatom records (Figure 4) and diatom record on the shelf (Sha et al., 2011). At this point, the diatom assemblages became dominated by the genus *Fragilariopsis*, which is associated with cold and stratified sea-surface waters and typically blooms in the early spring when ice starts to break-up and melt (von Quillfeldt, 2000, 2004; Oksman et al., 2019; Luostarinen et al., 2023). On the contrary, the relative abundances of the warmer-water indicator *Thalassionema nitschioides* and *R. hebetata* f. *semispina* in core 64G decreases markedly at this time (Figure 5) suggesting cooling of sea-surface temperatures and possibly reduced influence of Atlantic waters at the core site. Another sediment record from the adjacent Ameralik fjord shows identical cooling and freshening of the surface waters at the time, and a significant increase in the abundance of *Fragilariopsis* (Seidenkrantz et al., 2007) that might possibly be caused by the onset of lake Isvand draining through Austmannadalen.

As a result of continuing climate cooling (Figure 6), KNS advanced further in the fjord forming an ice-dammed lake in front of Qamanaarsuup Sermia (Figure 7) between 1181 and 1278 CE (Pearce et al., 2022; Weidick et al., 2012). The cold climate likely limited meltwater discharge into the fjord, which limited fjord productivity at this time. Together with wind-driven upwelling, subglacial meltwater discharge from marine-terminating glaciers provides essential nutrients (e.g., nitrate) for primary producers and is especially important for fueling the summer (second) phytoplankton bloom in Nuup Kangerlua (Juul-Pedersen et al., 2015; Meire et al., 2016, 2017; Stuart-Lee et al., 2023). The *Fragilariopsis* species, that mainly represent early-spring bloomers in fjord settings, dominated the assemblage between 1200 and 1600 CE (Figure 4) indicating relatively cold and strongly stratified sea-surface waters. This is consistent with other diatom records from southwest Greenland showing increased abundances of *Fragilariopsis* and cold sea-surface conditions at this time (Jensen et al., 2004; Seidenkrantz et al., 2007). The surface waters were likely nutrient-depleted after the extensive spring bloom, while the cold climate limited summer melting, further restricting the formation of the summer bloom and keeping the annual

production window short. Subglacial meltwater plumes typically settle below a fresher surface layer, however, the strong stratification (indicated by the *Fragilariopsis* spp.) might have prevented deep-water nutrients entering the necessary water-depth for phytoplankton growth. Similar stratified conditions are today created in fjords with land-terminating glaciers, for example, Ameralik fjord and the Young Sound, where meltwater runoff increases stratification that limits the summer bloom (Meire et al., 2017; Sejr et al., 2022; Stuart-Lee et al., 2023). In addition to changes in meltwater discharge, alterations in the glaciers grounding line depth and ocean heat content can also control the influence of subglacial plumes (Carroll et al., 2016). The cooling of fjord waters and strong stratification are likely to have played a role in reducing the overall productivity in the fjord during the late Neoglacial.

Our record shows that fjord conditions in Nuup Kangerlua became harsher at ca. 1600 CE (Figure 6). A decline in both BSi concentrations and fluxes, together with increasing IRD (Figure 6) suggests lower productivity and increased iceberg activity in the fjord. Higher abundances of marine centric diatoms (e.g., *D. confervacea* resting spore, *Bacterosira bathyomphala*, *T. nordenskiöldii*, and *Shionodiscus trifultus*), that are typical taxa for cold Arctic and sub-Arctic regions (Oksman et al., 2019; Pearce et al., 2014), further suggest cooler conditions. Additionally, the vegetative cells of *T. antarctica* var. *borealis* were largely replaced by resting spores at this point (Figure 4), which suggest unfavorable conditions. The formation of resting spores in Arctic planktic diatoms is partly a strategy to survive harsh conditions (von Quillfeldt, 1997) as resting spores promote the resilience and adaptability of species on multidecadal time scales (Ellegaard & Ribeiro, 2018). The diatom sample scores for the first CA axis show important shifts at this point in both sediment records (Figure 6) suggesting a significant turnover in the assemblage composition and, by inference, in the environmental conditions. Previous studies have proposed that the KNS margin reached its LIA maximum extent by the sill (Figure 7) latest at 1761 CE (Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, Weidick, et al., 2014; Pearce et al., 2022; Weidick et al., 2012). Based on the change in the diatom assemblage composition and fjord productivity (Figures 4 and 6), it seems plausible that KNS might have advanced to its maximum extent already at ca. 1600 CE, thus having an influence on the water column structure and possibly limiting nutrient availability for the primary producers.

4.4. Low Productivity During the Little Ice Age Retreat Phase and Post-1900 Recovery

From our proxy records, fjord productivity was at its lowest between 1750 and 1900 CE (Figure 6) during the period when glaciers in Nuup Kangerlua started to retreat from their maximum LIA extent. During this phase, KNS is known to have retreated over 22 km (Figures 6 and 7) from its LIA maximum extent to close to its modern-day position (Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, As, et al., 2014; Weidick et al., 2012). Half of this retreat occurred between 1808 and 1859 CE (Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, As, et al., 2014; Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, Weidick, et al., 2014; Pearce et al., 2022; Weidick et al., 2012) when our records suggest the lowest productivity levels of the Neoglacial record (Figures 5 and 6). These low TOC and BSi values in the sediment cores postdate the atmospheric temperature minima (Figure 6) and the period of low fjord productivity occurred under slowly warming climate conditions when glacial melt rates and subglacial discharge were likely increasing, which in turn based on modern observations should have a positive impact on fjord production (Hopwood et al., 2018; Meire et al., 2017). Our record suggest that glacier retreat and its impact on the fjord hydrography might have exerted a stronger control on the fjord productivity than climate. The rapid retreat likely created hydrographic conditions, where only little nutrients reached the primary producers in the surface waters. During the LIA retreat phase, diatom assemblages were mainly dominated by the resting stages of *T. antarctica* var. *borealis* and *D. confervacea*, and by other Arctic cold-water species, for example, *F. cylindrus* and *T. nordenskiöldii* (Figure 4) indicating a cold and harsh environment with stratified water column.

The glacier's grounding line depth defines the depth at which meltwater enters the water column and the hydrographic conditions at the glacier-proximal area which influence primary production (Hopwood et al., 2018). KNS grounding line depth has varied between 383 and 125 m water depth (Figure 7) during its retreat from the LIA maximum extent to the modern grounding line depth at <250 m (Mortensen et al., 2013). These changes should not be significant enough to impose direct influence on productivity in relation to upwelling of nutrient-rich deeper water, when compared to grounding line depths of other Greenlandic fjords (Hopwood et al., 2018). Modeling of the KNS frontline stability (Pearce et al., 2022) shows that KNS was relatively unstable during the main retreat phase between 1808 and 1859 CE (Figure 7), which is consistent with high IRD content in both cores (Figure 6) suggesting increased iceberg discharge at both study locations. Iceberg discharge can have a positive impact on primary production by local upwelling (Duprat et al., 2016; Vernet et al., 2012; Wu & Hou, 2017), yet

these findings are mainly from open ocean environments while not many studies exist from fjords (Kanna et al., 2018). Additionally, in fjords with marine-terminating glaciers, iceberg melt is a significant source of freshwater and icebergs have been found to be important in modifying the fjord water column by contributing to cooling and freshening of the uppermost 50 m and increasing stratification (Kajanto et al., 2023). It is thus plausible that the KNS unstable front margin and high iceberg discharge would have modified the hydrographic conditions and that (due to a strong stratification and insufficient wind strength) only minimal nutrient delivery would have reached the surface waters thus limiting primary production.

After the main LIA retreat phase between 1750 and 1900 CE, the fjord productivity rapidly increased (Figure 6). This change in the early 1900s is unprecedented in our 3,300 years-long record as the rapid increase in BSi, TOC, and diatom productivity occurred within decades (Figure 6) highlighting that fjord productivity recovered rapidly after the millennia-scale decline. The high productivity of the early 1900s likely reflects the increase of local air temperatures and sea-surface temperatures which increased markedly during the 1920–1930s (Buch, 2000; Ribergaard, 2014). The warm climate promoted a substantial retreat of the KNS margin of about 8 km between 1921 and 1948 (Lea, Mair, Nick, Rea, As, et al., 2014), which must have released significant amounts of meltwater into the fjord. Freshwater discharge has influenced the fjord productivity on a decadal scale during the last ca. 100 years (Oksman et al., 2022).

5. Conclusions

Long-term records of past fjord productivity are needed to understand how climate variability and a changing cryosphere will influence coastal primary productivity in a rapidly changing climate. Based on our Neoglacial fjord record, we find that productivity levels in Nuup Kangerlua overall follow the regional climate variability, and associated changes in the cryosphere, however, this relationship is not linear. Productivity was likely higher during the early Neoglacial period when diatom species composition suggest mild sea-surface conditions with a marked summer bloom. We find that warmer climate conditions and enhanced meltwater discharge, especially during the Medieval Climate Anomaly between 1.0 and 0.7 ka BP maintained relatively higher fjord productivity, whereas, cooling and more extensive sea ice at 2.8–2.2 ka BP led to a decrease in fjord productivity.

A shift in the diatom assemblage and a decline in productivity proxies ca. 2.0 ka BP indicates a transition into cooler sea-surface conditions and lower productivity. Our records show that fjord productivity gradually decreased along the cooling climate conditions during the last millennium and until the 1900s. Diatom assemblages suggest restricted summer blooms under cooler climate, and increased stratification which likely limited nutrient availability at the surface. Changes in the diatom species composition coincide with documented historical glacier front margin changes, and suggest that sea-surface conditions in Nuup Kangerlua became cold and harsh at ca. 1600, when KNS advanced to and stabilized at its LIA maximum extent. The lowest productivity levels of the Neoglacial record occur at the end of the Little Ice Age period ca. 1850 CE. A rapid recovery of the fjord productivity after 1900 CE represents a fast and unprecedented change in our record, likely driven by warming air-temperatures and increased melt from glacier termini. Our records indicate that, in Nuup Kangerlua, long-term changes in fjord primary productivity have mainly been driven by climate variability and associated changes in the glacier dynamics linked to subglacial meltwater discharge.

Data Availability Statement

Data presented in this paper are available in the GEUS dataverse (Oksman, 2024).

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